

QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF L-ARGININE HYDROCHLORIDE IN THE DRUG "ESCILAR" BY THE TITRATION METHOD

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Relevance: High drug quality is one of the most important criteria for producing a highly effective and safe medication. In modern medicine, medications containing amino acids are widely used for the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of many diseases. Compared to more complex methods, titration offers a good price-performance ratio, being a more accessible method of quantitative analysis. This method allows for the determination of substance content with high accuracy, down to hundredths of a milligram. Compared to more complex methods, titration offers a good price-performance ratio, being a more accessible method of quantitative analysis. Therefore, the use of titration remains relevant and in demand today.

Purpose of the study: The aim of the study is to develop a method for the quantitative determination of L-arginine hydrochloride in the combined infusion drug "Escilar", the active ingredient of which is L-arginine hydrochloride and escin.

Materials and methods: The drug "Escilar", an infusion solution, whose active substance is L-arginine hydrochloride and escin, was used as the object of the study.

10.0 ml of the sample is transferred to a 100 ml flask and titrated with 0.1 M silver nitrate solution until an orange-yellow color is achieved. Potassium chromate solution is used as an indicator.

The content of L-arginine chloride in 1 ml of the drug (X), in milligrams, is calculated using the following formula:

$$X = \frac{V \cdot K \cdot 21,07}{10},$$

where: V is the volume of titrant used for titration, in ml;

K -correction factor for titrated solution;

21.07 is the amount of sodium chloride in milligrams corresponding to 1 ml of 0.1 M silver nitrate solution.

All used reagents and titrated solutions, indicators are described in the relevant section of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Based on the studies conducted, it was established that the content of L-arginine hydrochloride (C₆H₁₄N₄O₂·HCl) in 1 ml of the drug should be from 27 mg to 33 mg.

Results: The study found that the average amount of L-arginine hydrochloride in 5 batches of the combined infusion preparation was 30 mg/ml and met the established criteria from 27 mg/ml to 33 mg/ml.

Conclusions: Based on the conducted studies, it was established that the developed method can be used for the quantitative determination of L-arginine hydrochloride in a combined infusion solution, as the obtained results are reliable and valid. The presence of other active components of the drug does not affect the analysis results. The method has been incorporated into the company's draft pharmacopoeial monograph.